

STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF SODIUM SULFIDE OBTAINED FROM OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION WASTE

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Abstract. Experiments were carried out in a chemical laboratory to obtain sodium sulfide from natural gas processing waste, which contains hydrogen sulfide.

As you know, hydrogen sulfide is a harmful substance that is released in many industries. Issues of cleaning, neutralization, disposal, or use of hydrogen sulfide as a raw material by industrial enterprises are an integral part of the problem of environmental protection. One of the pressing problems of our time is environmental protection [1].

Keywords: coke oven gas, sodium hydrosulfide, sodium sulfide, hydrogen sulfide, sodium hydroxide, flotation, leaching, Kipp apparatus, burette, magnetic stirrer, absorption, polysulfides, humic substances, brown coals.

Methods: Salts of the sulfide series include derivatives of hydrogen sulfide (sulfides), hydrogen polysulfides (polysulfides), as well as oxysulfides of the RO • RS type. They are widespread in nature and are raw materials for the production of non-ferrous metals and sulfuric acid. These include sulfides of copper, lead, silver, zinc, nickel, cobalt, iron, arsenic, antimony, mercury, etc. Natural sulfides are insoluble in water. The most important sulfide products obtained by industrial methods or formed during the purification of industrial gases from hydrogen sulfide are soluble compounds of alkali metals [2].

This work examines the production of sodium sulfide from natural gas purification wastes that contain hydrogen sulfide.

Sodium sulfide serves as a raw material for the production of sulfur dyes; it is used in the textile industry when dyeing cotton fabrics with these dyes, in the leather industry for removing hair from hides, and in the production of paints.

It is used mainly in flotation processes, in particular in the flotation of copper-zinc ores containing iron, zinc, and lead. Experiments are described for replacing sodium hydroxide with sodium sulfide during the chemical treatment of clay solutions for leaching humic substances from brown coals. Sodium sulfide is an intermediate in some methods for producing soda and sodium hydroxide from sodium sulfate [4].

Technical sodium sulfide is produced in the form of a fused product in iron drums or flaked in plastic bags.

Table 1.

№	Name	premium	1st grade	2nd grade
1	Sodium sulfide (Na ₂ S), not less	70	66	63
2	Substances insoluble in water, no more	0,2	0,5	1,5
3	Iron (Fe), no more	0,08	0,15	0,45

Sodium sulfide is obtained mainly by reducing sodium sulfate with coal. The resulting melt contains, in addition to Na₂S, significant amounts of impurities, to remove of which it is subjected

to leaching. The resulting solution of sodium sulfide is separated from unreacted coal and other insoluble substances and subjected to evaporation, during which the solution is purified from soluble compounds. The concentrated solution is poured into drums, where it solidifies into a product called fused sodium sulfide.

Relatively small amounts of sodium sulfide are obtained not by the reduction of sodium sulfate but by other methods.

Sodium sulfide is also obtained by processing CaS-containing waste dumps generated in the production of soda from sodium sulfate, limestone, and coal in the production of barium chloride using the calcium chloride method. When these dumps are boiled in a solution containing soda and sodium sulfate, CaS hydrolysis occurs.

When a solution of caustic soda traps waste hydrogen sulfide, obtained, for example, during production, oil refining or hydrogen sulfide extracted from coke ovens and other industrial gases, sodium sulfide is formed [5].

Experiments have been carried out to obtain sodium sulfide from local raw materials, that is, hydrogen sulfide, by absorbing sodium hydroxide into a solution. One of the pressing problems of our time is environmental protection.[6] As you know, hydrogen sulfide is a harmful substance that is released in many industries. Issues of cleaning, neutralization, disposal, or use of hydrogen sulfide as a raw material by industrial enterprises are an integral part of the problem of environmental protection.[7]

When waste hydrogen sulfide obtained during the production of barium, chloride is captured with a solution of caustic soda during the purification of oil or hydrogen sulfide extracted from coke ovens and other industrial gases, sodium hydrosulfide or sodium sulfide is formed.

Several experiments were carried out, and analyses were carried out on their basis; they showed that the sodium sulfide content in the resulting sample was 80%.

Fig. 1. Curve of increase in sodium sulfide content in solution

Experiments were carried out at different concentrations of sodium hydroxide solution.

Conclusion

Sodium sulfide is not produced in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Sodium sulfide is imported from foreign countries.[8]

The introduction into production, based on the experiments carried out, of producing sodium sulfide from hydrogen sulfide solves the issues of import substitution of this product and the environmental problem.

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